

DESIGN AND TESTING OF IN-SITU CONSOLIDATED THICK HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY: The Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) initiated a major technology effort to develop and demonstrate cost-effective, advanced fabrication methods for high performance, thick, graphite composite applications for future marine structures. One of the lower cost fabrication methods explored was auto-consolidated fiber placement of graphite thermoplastics. However, because the as-fabricated structure has material properties and strengths significantly different from flat autoclave consolidated coupons, a material characterization process was developed which quantified as-fabricated material properties, strengths and allowables for design. This paper presents the results of the comparison between auto-consolidated and autoclaved graphite thermoplastics, AS4/PPS and AS4/PEEK. This work was sponsored by DARPA and Office of Naval Research.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastics, evaluation, testing, in-situ consolidation, material characterization, design

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials offer the potential for reduced structural weight, improved corrosion resistance and associated reduction in maintenance and enhanced stealth and survivability over existing metals for marine structures. However, the composites selected must also demonstrate their benefits at competitive costs with present systems. Recognizing the benefits of composites, DARPA initiated a major technology effort in developing and demonstrating affordable composite fabrication processes for marine structures [1]. The objective of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) Composite Dry Deck Shelter (CDDS) program was to develop the technologies, experience and confidence needed to exploit the benefits and potentials of composite materials for advanced marine pressure hulls, structures and components through the transfer of proven aerospace composites technology. An interactive, three phase program was established to develop and demonstrate thick composites technologies progressing from design/concept

to fabrication and testing of sub-scale composite models in order to fully develop the technology for a proof-of-concept demonstration. The first phase of the program involved the development of material properties and allowables for the fabrication methods and materials selected. This data was then used to design, fabricate, test and evaluate 1.2m (48 in) diameter scale model pressure hull components [2] [3].

Fig.1 In-Situ Consolidation Process

Material Property	Lay-up	Thick-ness (in.)	Specimen	Number of .Specimens			
				Dry		Wet	
				28° F	RT	RT	140° F
1 - Tension $F_1^{tu}, E_1^t,$ $\epsilon_1^{tu}, \nu_{12}^t$	[0 ₈]	0.05		0	15	0	0
1 - Compression $F_1^{cu}, E_1^c,$ $\epsilon_1^{cu}, \nu_{12}^c$	[0 ₂₀]	0.12		5	15	5	5
2- Tension $F_2^{tu}, E_2^t,$ ϵ_2^{tu}	[90 ₂₀]	0.12		0	15	5	0
2 - Compression $F_2^{cu}, E_2^c,$ ϵ_2^{cu}	[0 ₂₀]	0.12		0	15	0	0
In-Plane Shear $F_1^{cu}, E_1^c,$ $\epsilon_1^{cu}, \nu_{12}^c$	[±45] _{2S}	0.05		0	15	5	0
Interlaminar Shear $F_2^{su}, G_{12}, \gamma_{12}^{su}$	[0 ₂₀]	0.12		5	15	5	5
Flatwise Tension F_3^{tu}	[±45] _{2S}	0.05		0	15	0	0

Fig. 2 - AS4/PPS Autoclave Lamina Test Matrix

Thermoplastic fiber placement processing (Fig. 1) was selected as the high quality, low cost manufacturing process. The in-situ consolidation process utilizes heat energy to simultaneously melt incoming feed material and the surface of the previously consolidated material. A pressure applicator then consolidates the thermoplastic in-situ and requires no further oven or autoclave processing [4]. A series of in-situ consolidated fiber placement AS4/PEEK material characterization and sub-element tests were conducted to confirm material knock-down factors and allowables. An investigation of a lower cost graphite thermoplastic, AS4/PPS, was initiated in an effort to reduce material and processing costs and increase fiber placement throughput. The initial material characterization of AS4/PPS involved similar tests to those established for the AS4/PEEK material characterization and included fabrication and testing of panels, implosion rings, burst rings, double notched shear specimens, and Joint Army Navy NASA Air Force (JANNAF) tubes [5]. Phase II of the AS4/PPS material characterization, which is discussed in this paper,

involves mechanical tests on compression, open hole compression, flexure, and interlaminar shear (ILS) specimens machined from a 1.22 m diameter in-situ consolidated Material Characterization Cylinder (MCC) (Fig. 4) as well as autoclave consolidated lamina and laminate specimens results (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Test Type	Lay-Up	Thickness (in)	Specimen	Data Required	No. of Specimens		Evaluation Emphasis
					RT/D	RT/W	
Compression	$[0/\pm 45/90]_{ns}$	0.250		$F_x^{cu}, \epsilon_x^{cu}$ E_x^c, ν_{xy}^c	10	10	Fiber/Matrix Interface
Open Hole Compression	$[0/\pm 45/90]_{ns}$	0.250		ϵ_x^{cu}, E_x^c	10	10	Stress Riser
Interlaminar Shear	$[0/\pm 45/90]_{ns}$	0.250		F_{xz}^{su}	5	5	"Z" Direction Resin Strength

Fig. 3 AS4/PPS Autoclave Laminate Test Matrix

Fig. 4 AS4/PPS Material Characterization Cylinder and Specimens

DISCUSSION OF TEST PROCEDURES

The repetition of standardized tests on different batches of materials or on the same material form from different vendors is required to establish statistically reliable material properties. The goal for the AS4/PPS material characterization studies was to determine baseline and as-fabricated material properties for AS4/PPS from different vendors and for comparison to AS4/PEEK. The methodology utilized in the testing was incorporated in order to evaluate environmental effects on the material and to investigate the material behavior as a part of a proof-of-concept prototype. In order to develop a baseline material

behavior, autoclave consolidated lamina and laminate flat specimens were fabricated and conditioned under numerous environmental conditions, which included moisture, temperature and pressure. In the case of AS4/PEEK, a large database on autoclave consolidated material properties and strengths was available for comparison. However for AS4/PPS no such database existed so it was necessary to perform testing on autoclave consolidated lamina and laminate specimens. Furthermore, specimens were taken from two, 1.2m (48 in) diameter, in-situ consolidated, fiber placed cylinders fabricated using hot gas torch and YAG laser, respectively, to evaluate the as-fabricated behavior of the material and compare the as-fabricated properties to the baseline properties.

Autoclave Consolidated Lamina and Laminate Tests

The AS4/PPS lamina tests included a total of 290 specimens. The dry specimens were placed in an oven and exposed to dry air at 60° C for five days. Wet specimens were exposed to 60° C sea water until equilibrium was reached which occurred after 146 days. Laminate property data was also obtained on hand laid-up, AS4/PPS autoclave panels. A total of 158 laminate specimens were tested. As with the lamina specimens, the dry specimens were placed in an oven and exposed to dry air at 60° C for five days while the wet specimens were exposed to 60° C sea water until equilibrium was reached. Laminate wet specimens reached equilibrium after only 129 days.

AS4/PPS Material Characterization Cylinder

The in-situ fiber placed Material Characterization Cylinders were fabricated using ADC's hot gas torch head for Cytec Fiberite PPS and YAG laser for the Quadrax PPS. The cylinders were approximately 6.3 mm (0.25 inches) thick and had a lay-up of $[90_2, \pm 45, (0, 90_2)_4, \pm 45]_S$, or $(22.2\% 0^\circ, 22.2\% \pm 45^\circ, 55.6\% 90^\circ)$, where 0° was along the longitudinal axis. Ultrasonic inspection was performed and C-scans were produced to determine the locations of test specimens to be machined. A total of 84 test specimens from highest quality to poor quality were machined from each MCC using a water jet machining process. Wet and dry specimen tests were conducted on the MCC specimens. Moisture conditioning of the wet specimens involved, for one case (WET1), immersion in 60° C sea water at 1 bar (15 psi), and for the second case (WET2), immersion in room temperature sea water at 17.2 Mpa (2,500 psi). The WET1 specimens were exposed to their respective environmental conditions for approximately 190 days. The WET2 specimens were exposed for approximately 5 1/2 months. The moisture conditioning was performed on the specimens at Carderock Division/Naval Surface Warfare Center (CD/NSWC). Boeing St. Louis (BSL) conducted all the tests on the AS4/PPS MCC using lessons learned for AS4/PEEK MCC tested earlier [5]. This testing required the use of specialized testing fixtures due to curvature of the specimens (Figs. 5 –9).

Fig. 5 - MCC Interlaminar Shear Specimen Test and Set-Up

Fig. 6 - MCC Flexural Test Specimen and Set-Up

Fig. 7 - MCC Compression Test Specimen

Fig. 8 - MCC Open Hole Compression Test Specimen

Fig. 9 - MCC Support Fixtures for Compression and OHC Tests

DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

AS4/PPS Autoclave Lamina Tests

The lamina specimen tests included axial compression, transverse tension, and ILS strength tests. Details of the inspection, testing and tests results by EBC, BSL and Albany International Research Company (AIRESKO) are presented in [6]. The results tend to show the effect of temperature and moisture. On the average, dry room temperature specimens out-performed, wet specimens by approximately 15%. A summary of typical lamina test results is given in Table 1. Also included in the table are the results of the previously tested AS4/PEEK material. In order to both create a basis for comparison, as well as, to extrapolate lamina values for as-fabricated conditions, it was necessary to apply correction factors to account for the differences in fiber volume. These final properties are compiled and compared to the AS4/PEEK values in Table 2.

Test	Lay-Up	Property	AS4/PEEK 60% FV ¹	AS4/PEEK 50% FV ²	AS4/PPS 50% FV ³
Tension	[0 ₈]	F ₁ ^{tu} (ksi)	298	248	256
		ε ₁ ^{tu} (μ in/in)	14,900	-	14,129
		E ₁ ^t (msi)	20.0	16.7	15.3
	[90 ₂₀]	F ₂ ^{tu} (ksi)	12.6	-	4.07
		ε ₂ ^{tu} (μ in/in)	8,690	-	3,162
		E ₂ ^t (msi)	1.45	1.17	1.30
Compression	[0 ₈]	F ₁ ^{cu} (ksi)	-175	-146	-131
		ε ₁ ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-10,940	-	-9,383
		E ₁ ^c (msi)	16.0	13.3	15.3
	[90 ₂₀]	F ₂ ^{cu} (ksi)	-33.6	-	-22.9
		ε ₂ ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-22,700	-	-
		E ₂ ^c (msi)	1.48	1.20	1.29
ILS	[0 ₂₀]	F ₁₃ ^{su} (ksi)	18.4	-	12.1
IPS	[±45] _{2S}	F ₁₂ ^{su} (ksi)	27.1	-	14.9
		ε ₁₂ ^{su} (μ in/in)	32,700	-	-
		G ₁₂ (msi)	0.83	-	0.55
Flatwise Tension	[±45] _{2S}	F ₃ ^{tu} (ksi)	-	-	4.21

- Notes: (1) - Measured fiber volume
(2) - Normalized to 50% fiber volume
(3) - Approximate fiber volume

Table 1. Autoclave AS4/PPS and AS4/PEEK Lamina Test Results

Property Type	AS4/PEEK	AS4/PPS
Unnotched Compression	-7,070 μ in/in	-6,390 μ in/in
Interlaminar Shear	12,000 psi	7,740 psi
Interlaminar Tension	3,090 psi	2,290 psi

Table 2. AS4/PPS and AS4/PEEK Estimated Fiber Placed Lamina Allowables

AS4/PPS Autoclave Laminate Tests

The laminate specimen tests included axial compression, open hole compression, and ILS strength tests for dry and wet conditioning. All laminate testing was done for specimens at 24° C. Unlike the lamina results, no general relationship was observed in the laminate tests between strength and amount of moisture conditioning. Higher average properties were seen for some of the wet specimens. This behavior was also noted in the testing of AS4/PEEK moisture conditioned specimens. The Quadrax AS4/PPS laminate tests included investigations involving three distinct lay-ups. The first lay-up was a [0₂,90]_{8S} cross-ply configuration, the second set of laminates had a [0,±45,90]_{6S} quasi-isotropic lay-up, and the third lay-up was identical to that used for the MCC. Void content measurements were less than one percent. Laminate test specimens for each lay-up and conditioning case were compression tested. The data suggests that wet conditioning had little effect on the quasi-isotropic compression strength. However, as expected, dry specimens showed generally higher values than those which were moisture conditioned.

It was noted by Boeing and AIRESCO that significant micro-cracking occurred in the AS4/PPS laminate panels for both vendors. The C-scans of the quasi-isotropic panels

showed abnormally high levels of base attenuation, indicating the presence of micro-cracking. Micro-cracking in the quasi-isotropic panels was first suspected during removal from their respective autoclave runs. It was observed that while cooling each panel emitted very audible cracking noises. The unidirectional panels showed no such micro-cracking problem. The micro-cracking is felt to be caused by the low transverse shear strength of the PPS resin and the large difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between the fiber and the resin. During cool down large thermal stresses are introduced by the graphite fiber into the resin and due to the low PPS shear the resin fractures. This micro-cracking phenomena is a potential cause for concern regarding the durability of this material in an autoclave cure. A summary of all the Quadrax and Cytec Fiberite AS4/PPS and AS4/PEEK autoclave laminate test results is included in Table 3. Based on a comparison of BSL test results for the Quadrax AS4/PPS and Cytec Fiberite AS4/PEEK materials and the AIRESCO Cytec Fiberite AS4/PPS material, the AS4/PPS properties are lower than those for AS4/PEEK. This is in part due to the fact that the AS4/PPS had a lower fiber volume than the AS4/PEEK.

Test	Lay-Up	Property	AS4/PEEK		AS4/PPS			
					Quadrax		Fiberite	
			RTD	RTW	RTD	RTW	RTD	RTW
Unnotched Compression	[0 ₂ ,90] _{8S}	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-95.9	-104.0	-100.8	-82.1	-	-
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-8,993	-9,858	-9,901	-8,507	-	-
		E _x ^c (msi)	11.44	11.42	10.18	9.69	-	-
	[0,±45,90] _{6S}	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-67.9	-67.8	-63.5	-64.3	-57.3	-57.1
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-11,553	-10,950	-12,388	-12,549	-9,700	-9,900
		E _x ^c (msi)	6.51	6.64	5.78	5.48	6.50	6.20
	MCC	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-	-	-54.8	-51.7	-	-
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-	-	-14,400	-12,375	-	-
		E _x ^c (msi)	-	-	-4.44	-4.54	-	-
Open Hole Compression	[0 ₂ ,90] _{8S}	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-57.0	-58.1	-51.4	-48.8	-	-
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-4,602	-4,633	-4,647	-4,471	-	-
		E _x ^c (msi)	12.3	12.45	11.02	10.75	-	-
	[0,±45,90] _{6S}	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-55.1	-53.9	-39.3	-39.3	-37.9	-38.3
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-8,617	-8,462	-7,481	-7,709	-6,000	-6,100
		E _x ^c (msi)	6.84	6.84	5.43	5.27	6.70	6.50
	MCC	F _x ^{cu} (ksi)	-	-	-27.6	-28.4	-	-
		ε _x ^{cu} (μ in/in)	-	-	-6,330	-6,459	-	-
		E _x ^c (msi)	-	-	-4.45	-4.56	-	-
Interlaminar Shear	[0 ₂ ,90] _{8S}	F _{xz} ^{su} (ksi)	15.6	16.0	10.3	8.39	-	-
	[0,±45,90] _{6S}	F _{xz} ^{su} (ksi)	16.3	16.2	9.63	7.25	4.78	5.14
	MCC	F _{xz} ^{su} (ksi)	-	-	7.10	5.60	-	-

Table 3 - Autoclave AS4/PPS and AS4/PEEK Laminate Test Results

Comparison of Autoclave Lamina and Laminate Test Results

Since dry lamina specimens showed, on average, only slightly higher properties than the wet lamina specimens, moisture absorption has little effect on lamina strength, which is consistent with other research and testing on graphite thermoplastics. A more noticeable difference is seen when comparing two specimens tested at different temperatures, where elevated temperatures show a decrease in strength. Furthermore, a comparison between the test specimens shows that the average maximum stress and stiffness in the lamina specimens is roughly twice that of the laminate specimens under both ILS and compressive load conditions. Although much of the difference in strength is attributed to the different lay-up and number of on-axis fibers, micro-cracking was observed in the quasi-isotropic specimens during the autoclave cycle and is considered to be a major contributor to the weaker properties of this lay-up.

AS4/PPS Fiber Placed Material Characterization Cylinder Tests

Boeing performed mechanical property tests on specimens machined from the AS4/PPS Material Characterization Cylinders. Due to the residual thermal strains developed during fabrication, the test set-ups had to be altered to adjust for bowing of the specimens. An example of this bowing, as well as an illustration showing the corrective action required, is included in Figure 10.

Both the open hole compression and unnotched compression specimens exhibited bowing which required adjustment of the test fixture. The unnotched compression specimens had an average thermal strain of $-781 \mu \text{ in/in}$ at the inner mold line (IML) and $+898 \mu \text{ in/in}$ at the outer mold line (OML). The average residual strain in the OHC specimens was $-591 \mu \text{ in/in}$ at the IML and $+675 \mu \text{ in/in}$ at the OML. These specimens were forced flat prior to testing. A comparison of the unnotched compression, open hole compression, flexure and interlaminar shear test results for the AS4/PEEK and AS4/PPS MMC specimens and Cytec Fiberite AS4/PPS MCC are presented in Table 4. When compared to AS4/PEEK results, it can be seen that the AS4/PPS mechanical properties are lower by as much as 23%, with Quadrax and Cytec Fiberite AS4/PPS properties being essential equivalent.

Fig. 10 AS4/PPS MCC Specimen Bowing Due to Residual Strains

As can be seen from Table 4, the AS4/PPS interlaminar shear (ILS) specimen tests for both the Quadrax and Cytec Fiberite material showed about 25% lower strength than the AS4/PEEK MCC specimens. This lower strength can be largely attributed to the lower shear strength of the PPS resin system. The laser and hot gas torch AS4/PPS specimens showed essentially equivalent results, with the AS4/PEEK specimens having about 15% to 23% higher strength.

Average dry flatwise tension Cytec Fiberite results show tensile strength at 11.9 MPa (1,730 psi). The QUADRAX AS4/PPS flatwise tension strength had average strength of 12.8MPa (1,860 psi) with a standard deviation of 1.6 MPa (240 psi). The AS4/PPS lamina and laminate results were generally poorer than those for the AS4/PEEK materials.

Test	Property	AS4/PEEK (BSL) ¹		AS4/PPS			
				Quadrax (BSL) ²		Fiberite (EB) ³	
		Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet1	Dry	Wet1
Unnotched Compression	F_x^{cu} (ksi)	-51.6	-48.7	-41.8	-39.3	-39.8	-42.3
	ϵ_x^{cu} ($\mu \text{ in/in}$)	-10,363	-9,952	-8,859	-8,627	-8,796	-9,565
	E_x^c (msi)	5.50	5.47	4.96	4.80	4.77	4.78

Open Hole Compression	F_x^{cu} (ksi)	-34.1	-32.1	-25.3	-23.4	-26.5	-27.0
	ϵ_x^{cu} (μ in/in)	-6,360	-6,064	-5,068	-4,899	-5,645	-5,660
	E_x^c (msi)	5.58	5.46	5.03	4.78	4.75	4.81
Flexure	F_x^b (ksi)	69.5	77.7	58.8	-	57.7	58.1
	$ \epsilon_x^b $ (μ in/in)	15,215	14,142	13,295	-	13,485	12,732
	E_x^b (msi)	5.18	5.13	4.81	-	3.84	4.59
Interlaminar Shear	F_{xz}^{su} (ksi)	7.70	6.40	4.28	3.60	5.11	5.04
		Axial	Axial	Axial	Axial	Axial	Axial
		9.70		5.76	5.04	5.95	6.45
		Hoop		Hoop	Hoop	Hoop	Hoop

- Notes: (1)- Specimens machined from MDA MACSS with 55% fiber vol. and 4.38% void cont.
(2)- Similar to Note 1 but with Quadrax AS4/PPS and 51% FV and 1.45% VC
(3)- Similar to Note 1 but by ADC with Cytec Fiberite AS4/PPS and 50% FV and 3.82% VC

Table 4 - Fiber Placed AS4/PEEK and AS4/PPS Test Results

SUMMARY

Autoclaved lamina and laminate, as well as in-situ consolidated Material Characteristic Cylinder (MCC) specimen mechanical testing was performed on Quadrax and Cytec Fiberite brand AS4/PPS. Results of these tests reported herein showed the AS4/PPS strengths and properties to be lower than those of AS4/PEEK even though the AS4/PPS had shown consistently lower void contents. From this characterization and the experience gained from testing similar AS4/PEEK specimens and the four-foot diameter AS4/PEEK stiffened cylinder [3] [5], an assessment of the effects of using AS4/PPS in place of AS4/PEEK can be made. Results of material tests performed on the AS4/PPS and included in previous sections show it to possess lower mechanical properties when compared to AS4/PEEK. Although the material is less expensive, its poorer performance would require more material to match the qualities of the AS4/PEEK. In addition, the evidence of micro-cracking in both in-situ fiber placed specimens and autoclave specimens raises serious doubts about the durability of this material under cyclic loads. Therefore, the ONR Storage Module will continue to use the AS4/PEEK material and forego the option of the less expensive AS4/PPS material.

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